

TEXTING AND IT'S IMPLICATION ON ENGLISH GRAMMAR SKILL

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Texting and Its Implication on English Grammar Skill

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Abstract

In sending text messages on mobile phones, students often use a special type of register, called *textese*. This register allows the omission of words. It is possible that a student's grammar system is influenced by *textese* as well as grammar rules which are often transgressed in this register. This paper aimed to find out the implication of texting on the English grammar skills of grade 7 students. Specifically, the study sought to answer the problems of how the respondents were characterized in terms of texting characteristics and its duration, their level of English grammar skills, and the significant relationship between their texting characteristics and their English Grammar as well as the significant relationship between their exposure to texting and their English Grammar skills level. The study employed a qualitative-quantitative research method. Respondents were asked to answer the English Grammar test composed of 6 parts; Sentence structure, Syntax, Spelling, Capitalization, Punctuation, and Abbreviation. In analyzing the data objectively, the statistical tools used included frequency and percentage, mean, and Pearson-product moment. Based on the respondents' characteristics on text messaging, the grade 7 students spent about 1-6 hours a day, incurred occasional to frequent shortcut spellings, and tended to have 50% to 75% content use of English. Second, among the different competencies in English grammar, the results revealed Spelling as the highest while Sentence Structure was their weakest performance. Third, in the correlation analysis between exposure to text messaging in English in terms of duration of texting, frequency of shortcut words, extent of texting in English, and Level of English Grammar Skills, the three variables revealed negative low correlations. Hence, after an intensive analysis of the data, the study concluded that texting has negative implications on the English grammar skills of grade 7 students.

Keywords: *qualitative-quantitative, register, textese, sentence structure, spelling*

Introduction

With all the advances in communication over the last few decades, text messages have become a standard form of communication. Due to the fast and often short nature of SMS transmission, a new omitted register of communication called "SMS" has emerged. Students' increasing use of mobile phones has a particular impact on their literacy and language use. One known characteristic of students' text messages is that they no longer constantly adhere to traditional English Grammar rules (Nvan, 2016).

It is alarming that despite obtaining 3rd Rank across Asia as one of the best speaking countries in terms of English as Second Language (L2) but sadly, the Philippines has also been recorded as the least performing country in terms of English Proficiency in Writing as observed to past Achievement Tests (Crossley & McCarthy, 2010). Regarding English Proficiency in pursuit of two productive language domains, speaking and writing stress that students still find difficulty observing the correct use of grammar for effective communication through speaking and writing. Imagine how hard it would be when it comes to writing. Thus, an essay has been regarded as the most challenging skill to mold. Similar to the problems faced by most students in speaking, students still struggle in observing grammar structures that affect their skills in English grammar.

In the case of the school where the researcher was connected, it is a commonly observed that one of the most common mistakes students make was on the use of proper grammar in their writing activities. A few phrases that the students used in their writing activities are not suitable for formal writing. Moreover, most English teachers decide students' essays to be entire with pointless and irrelevant fillers and lousy sentence structure. However, the situation with this case is that if it remains whether or not or now no longer, it is going to influence the overall skills in writing and speaking the usage of the Standard English language and the English grammar use. It is rampant in every school-observing students using their mobile phones during their free time. They used to spend most of their time texting instead of spending time in the library reading books for them to enrich their vocabulary.

Further, this study aimed to find the implication of texting on English Grammar skills such as spelling, syntax, punctuation, abbreviations, capitalization, and sentence structure. A set of English Grammar tests was given to the students to determine whether this texting implies students' grammar skills. The test result became the basis to find out how strong this implication is on the English grammar skill of the students. This study also tried to investigate a significant relationship between texting language and English Grammar skills. In addition, whether text messaging was to be blamed for poor use of English Grammar skills of learners or there was a possibility of the involvement of other factors.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the implication of Texting on English Grammar Skills of the Grade 7 respondents during the school year 2021-2022. This specifically attempted to answer the following questions:

1. How are the respondents characterized in terms of:
 - 1.1. texting characteristics;
 - 1.1.1. type of text messages sent;
 - 1.1.2. Common words usually written in shortcut manner;
 - 1.1.3. Grammatical Structure in sending text messages;
 - 1.2. Exposure to text messaging;
 - 1.2.1. Duration of texting in English;
 - 1.2.2. Frequency of shortcut spelling use; and
 - 1.2.3. Extent of text messaging in English?
2. What is the level of English grammar skills of the Grade 7 respondents in terms of:
 - 2.1. spelling;
 - 2.2. syntax;
 - 2.3. sentence structure;
 - 2.4. abbreviation;
 - 2.5. punctuation; and
 - 2.6. capitalization?
3. Is there a significant relationship between texting characteristics and the English Grammar skills of Grade 7 students?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' exposure to texting and their English Grammar skills level?
5. Based on the findings what action plan can be drawn and be implemented to the Grade 7 students?

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a qualitative-quantitative research method. It is qualitative as it identified the level of respondents' English Grammar skills includes, including abbreviations, vocabulary, syntax, sentence structure, capitalization, punctuation, and spelling. Moreover, it is quantitative because a set of questionnaires were utilized to know the respondents texting characteristics and their consciousness of the use of English grammar in texting.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were the Grade 7 students who were currently enrolled in S.Y 2021-2022 in one of the most outstanding schools in Bukidnon. There were three sections in the Grade 7 curriculum with English Subjects. Thirty students participated in the pilot testing, and 101 students participated in the actual gathering of data. Using the tables below, the texting language profile and grammar test scores were tallied per student respondent.

Table 1. *Respondents of the Study*

<i>Section</i>	<i>Number of Students</i>
Daisy	33
Tulips	36
Carnation	32
Total	101

Instrument

The study was qualitative-quantitative. The researcher employed a questionnaire to encompass parts. The first part consisted of personal-associated questions on the students' texting profiles the respondents and questions associated with the respondents. The researcher modified the questionnaire, and she adopted it in the study of Archibido and Mones (2016). Some parts that have been modified in the questionnaire were: A. Duration of texting in English; B. Frequent use of shortcut spelling; C. added the educational message as one of the options; D. provided the common words students usually use in shortcut spelling; and F. What is the extent of the text messaging in English added as an additional question in part 1 of the questionnaire.

The second part of the questionnaire was about the Grammar Test to identify the performance level of the respondents in English. The Grammar test covers spelling, syntax, abbreviation, sentence structure, capitalization, and punctuation. It was based on the Grammar Exercise from the book Prentice Hall Grammar and Composition. Some modifications happened in the Grammar test, the researcher made sure that the level of the grammar test would fit the respondents' knowledge.

Procedure

To achieve the data, the researcher conducted the following procedures:

The researcher sent a letter request or permission to the principal of the school. After the approval, the researcher approached the teachers of the grade 7 curriculum and asked them how to reach their students, especially during this pandemic. The researcher conducted the pilot testing and had the data tested for reliability. The research asked for the class lists of the students who were enrolled

in English subjects. The researcher allowed the students to answer the questionnaire and the English Grammar tests if the students were available. They were given 45 minutes to answer. After that, the researcher collected the questionnaires and test papers.

Scoring Procedure

To determine the English grammar skill of the Grade 7 respondents during the school year 2021-2022, the researcher used the respondents' school grading scale and its description. This was to measure the scores of spelling, syntax, abbreviation, sentence structure, capitalization, and punctuation of the respondents.

Table 2. *Scoring Procedure*

<i>English Grammar Test</i>	<i>Scores</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
Spelling	0-1	Poor
	3-5	Fair
	6-8	Satisfactory
	9-10	Very Satisfactory
Syntax	0-2	Poor
	3-5	Fair
	6-8	Satisfactory
	9-10	Very Satisfactory
Sentence Structure	0-2	Poor
	3-5	Fair
	6-8	Satisfactory
	9-10	Very Satisfactory
Abbreviation	0-2	Poor
	3-5	Fair
	6-8	Satisfactory
	9-10	Very Satisfactory
Punctuation	0-2	Poor
	3-5	Fair
	6-8	Satisfactory
	9-10	Very Satisfactory
Capitalization	0-2	Poor
	3-5	Fair
	6-8	Satisfactory
	9-10	Very Satisfactory
Over-all English Grammar Skill		
<i>Score</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Level</i>
0-15	Poor	Beginning Level
16-30	Fair	Developing Level
31-45	Satisfactory	Proficient Level
46-60	Very Satisfactory	Advanced Level

Data Analysis

To have an accurate interpretation of the obtained data, the following statistical tool were utilized:

Frequency and percentage distribution were employed to describe the respondents' profile in terms of their frequency of texting, shortcut of spelling use, and the type of text message sent. Although the number of alterations of English grammar committed by the 8th grade respondents is qualitative, however, frequency and percentage distribution will still be used.

Mean was used to determine the respondents' English grammar proficiency level.

Pearson-product moment correlation was utilized to test the strength, direction, nature and significance of relationship between significant relationship between texting characteristics and the English Grammar skills. Same as with Statement problem 4, a significant relationship between the respondents' exposure to texting and their English Grammar skills level.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the analysis, interpretation, and discussion of the results. The results are given based on the order of the problems of the study.

Problem 1. How are the respondents characterized in terms of: texting characteristics; type of text messages sent; Common words usually written in shortcut manner; and Grammatical Structure in sending text messages; Exposure to text messaging; Duration of texting in English; Frequency of shortcut spelling use; and Extent of text messaging in English?

Table 3 displayed the respondent's characteristics as defined by the type of text messages sent.

Table 3. Respondent Characteristics in terms of Type of Messages Sent

	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Standard Error of the Mean</i>
Personal	71	70.30	1.792	.779	.077
Inquiry	30	29.70			
Educational	66	65.35			
Jokes	32	31.68			
Spiritual	20	19.80			

The parameters were recorded as ordinal variables to measure the mean and standard deviation to fit the correlation requirements

As observed in the table above, through the open- and multiple option-multiple answer checklist, it was reported in table 3 that among the options, personal greetings and messages are widely utilized function of text messaging (f=71, 70.30%). This is marginally followed by the use of text messaging to inform others of educational information, f=66, 65.35%. A select number of the grade 7 learners have also reported that they have used text messaging to communicate jokes (f=32, 31.68%), inquiry (f=30, 29.70%) and spiritual information (f=20, 19.80%). When scaled to numerical conversions, the checks were counted reflecting each respondent in the study. The use of central tendency and variability statistics revealed that on average, the grade 7 learners chose at least one to two of the open and multiple options of how they utilize text messaging according to its type (M(101)=1.792, sd=.779, SEM=.127).

Similarly, in Cowart 2015 article. He stated that, text messaging is used for personal, family, business, social, and academic purposes. In addition, texting is commonly used by the learners to reach out to teachers and classmates about school matters. Not just learners, but including employees for personal use. Texting is used to communicate very quick messages, including greeting a person on birthdays or actually asking a person’s current situation.

Table 4 displayed the respondent’s characteristics as defined by the common words usually type in a shortcut manner.

Table 4. Respondent Characteristics in terms of Common words usually type in a shortcut manner

	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Standard Error of the Mean</i>
1. tonight – 2nite	9	8.91	3.178	1.884	.187
2. by the way – Btw	54	53.47			
3. tomorrow -2moro	6	5.94			
4. direct message – DM	40	39.60			
5. thank you – ty	51	50.50			
6. laugh out loud –LOL	32	31.68			
7. as soon as possible –ASAP	34	33.66			
8. also known as –AKA	19	18.81			
9. birthday –B-day	30	29.70			
10. at the moment – ATM	13	12.87			

The parameters were recoded as ordinal variables to measure the mean and standard deviation to fit the correlation requirements

Through the open- and multiple option-multiple answer checklist, it was reported in table 4 that among the options, “BTW-by the way” has been mostly used by the grade 7 learners, f=54, 53.47%. This has been followed by the use of “TY-thank you” as a shortcut response, f=51, 50.50%. A relative grade grades 7 learners have reported to have used, “ATM-at the moment” (f=13, 12.87%), “2nite-tonight” (f=9, 8.91%), “2moro-tomorrow” (f=6, 5.94%) as shortcut text messages When scaled to numerical conversions, the checks were counted reflecting each respondent in the study. The use of central tendency and variability statistics revealed that on the average, the grade 7 learners use at least three to at most five of the open and multiple options, which are the words they commonly shortcut when text messaging (M(101)=3.178, sd=1.884, SEM=.187).

Table 5 displayed the respondent’s characteristic as defined by their Consciousness to the grammatical structure when utilizing text messaging.

Table 5. Respondent Characteristics in terms of Grammatical Structure Consciousness

	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Standard Error of the Mean</i>
3-Yes, Always	8	7.92	1.851	.566	.056
2-Yes, Sometimes	70	69.30			
1-Never follow grammar	23	22.77			

The parameters were recoded as ordinal variables to measure the mean and standard deviation to fit the correlation requirements

It is reported from Table 5 that as much as 70 or 69.30% of the Grade 7 learners sometimes are conscious of grammar rules. This is followed by the group of 23 grade 7 learners who may not be conscious of grammar structure or rules at all, f=23. 22.77%. A relatively smaller portion of the group of grade 7 learners (f=18, 17.82%) has reported that they have always been conscious of grammar structure and rules when text messaging. When scaled to numerical conversions, the use of central tendency and variability statistics revealed that on average, the grade 7 learners tend to not be conscious to sometimes become conscious of grammar structure (M(101)=1.851, sd=.566, SEM=.056).

Hymes (2014) also added that texting can help students acquire fluency in English, it should come as no surprise that texting also benefits the writing skills of already fluent English speakers.

Table 6 illustrated the respondent's characteristic as defined by their duration of texting English in a day.

Table 6. *Respondent Characteristics in terms of Duration of Texting English*

	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Standard Error of the Mean</i>
Less than an hour a day	18	17.82	2.723	1.097	.109
1-3 hours a day	20	19.80			
4-6 hours a day	39	38.61			
7-9 hours a day	20	19.80			
Beyond 10 hours	4	3.96			

The parameters were recoded as ordinal variables to measure the mean and standard deviation to fit the correlation requirements

It is reported from Table 6 that as much as 39 or 38.61% of the Grade 7 learners spend 4-6 hours a day to communicate through texting. This is followed by the group of 20 grade 7 learners who use text messaging inasmuch as 1-3 hours a day and 7-9 hours a day. A relatively smaller portion of the group of grade 7 learners ($f=4$, 3.96%) have spent beyond 10 hours of text messaging in a day. When scaled to numerical conversions, the use of central tendency and variability statistics revealed that on the average, the grade 7 learners spent 1-6 hours a day of text messaging ($M(101)=2.723$, $sd=1.097$, $SEM=.109$).

With this, the result of the data shown above was also supported in the study of Sandvin (2010). He said that on common there are greater than 280,000 SMS messages sent per hour. This manner that greater than 6.7 million consistent with day send the ones messages with most effective four million populations. Among students, text message is the preferred form of mediated interaction, surpassing immediate messaging. Based on the data shown above, when scaled to numerical conversions, the use of central tendency and variability statistics revealed that on the average, the grade 7 learners spent 1-6 hours a day of text messaging ($M(101)=2.723$, $sd=1.097$, $SEM=.109$).

Table 7 illustrated the respondent's characteristic as defined by their frequency of shortcut spelling use.

Table 7. *Respondent Characteristics in terms of Frequency of shortcut spelling use*

	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Standard Error of the Mean</i>
6-Always	21	20.79	4.168	1.281	.127
5-Very Frequent	19	18.81			
4-Occasionally	27	26.73			
3-Rarely	24	23.76			
2-Very Rarely	10	9.90			
1-Never	0	0			

The parameters were recoded as interval variables to measure the mean and standard deviation to fit the correlation requirements

It is reported in table 7 that along the scale, 27 or 26.73% of the grade 7 learners "occasionally" shortcut the spelling when text messaging. This is followed by a group of Grade 7 learners who reported that they shortcut the spelling "rarely" ($f=24$, 23.76%) and marginally followed with those who "always" shortcut their spellings ($f=21$, 20.79%). However, only 10 or 9.90% of the grade 7 learners sported to "very rarely" shortcut their spellings in text messaging and no grade 7 learners have reported "never" in shortcuts of text messages. When scaled to numerical conversions, the use of central tendency and variability statistics revealed that on the average, the grade 7 learners occasionally to frequently shortcut spellings in text messaging ($M(101)=4.168$, $sd=1.281$, $SEM=.127$).

The result that has been illustrated above is supported by the study.

It is observed that most of the short textisms term are used by people in SMS language is compared to any other means of communication. He found out that, using of shortcut spelling influenced positively in the student's spelling. Out of 118 students there are 83 students who used the shortcut spelling in texting.

Table 8 displayed the respondent's characteristic as defined by their extent use of English text messaging.

Table 8. *Respondent Characteristics in terms of Extent of Use of English in Text Messaging*

	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Standard Error of the Mean</i>
4-100% English	0	0	2.733	.847	.084
3-75% English	53	52.48			
2-50% English	22	21.78			
1-25% English	26	25.74			

The parameters were recoded as ordinal variables to measure the mean and standard deviation to fit the correlation requirements

It is reported from Table 8 that as much as 53 or 52.48% of the Grade 7 learners use 75% of the English language while text messaging. This is followed by the group of 26 grade 7 learners who use 25% English of the time when text messaging, $f=26$, 25.74%. A marginally

smaller portion of the group of grade 7 learners ($f=22$, 21.78%) have reported that they have been utilizing 50% of English language while text messaging. When scaled to numerical conversions, the use of central tendency and variability statistics revealed that on the average, the grade 7 learners tend to use 50% to 75% content use of English language in their text messaging ($M(101)=2.733$, $sd=.847$, $SEM=.084$).

The data that has been illustrated below is supported with a published study conducted by Meachem, S., et al. (2011). Through assessments of academic language and analysis of a corpus of 44,597 text messages, the study found that emergent bilinguals who send more messages in English and choose English for the settings on their mobile phones tend to have higher academic English skills.

Problem 2. What is the level of English grammar skills of the Grade 7 respondents in terms of: Spelling; Syntax; Sentence Structure; Abbreviation; Punctuation; and Capitalization

Table 9 displayed the level of English grammar skills of the Grade 7 learners

Table 9. Level of English Grammar Skills of the Grade 7 Learners

	Mean	SD	Standard Error of the Mean	CI 95% Upper	CI 95% Lower	Interpretation
Spelling	7.59	2.07	.206	8.00	7.19	Satisfactory
Syntax	7.23	2.21	.220	7.66	6.80	Satisfactory
Sentence Structure	6.10	2.74	.272	6.63	5.57	Fair to Satisfactory
Abbreviation	7.04	2.21	.220	7.47	6.61	Satisfactory
Punctuation	6.36	2.04	.203	6.76	5.96	Satisfactory
Capitalization	6.86	1.76	.175	7.26	6.52	Satisfactory

The study revealed mean scores that are beyond the median of 5 indicating beyond average to proficient grammar skills. Among the different competence of English grammar, the results revealed highest competence is spelling, $M(101)=7.59$, $sd=2.07$, $SEM=.206$, falling within the satisfactory level (CI 95% = 7.19, 8.00). This indicates that the grade 7 learners are at the acceptable levels of being able to identify the correct spellings of essential English words while committing infrequent errors to more complex words.

This was marginally followed by the skill on syntax, $M(101)=7.23$, $sd=2.21$, $SEM=.220$, which is interpreted from the scale as a satisfactory level (CI 95% = 6.80, 7.66). This demonstrates that the grade 7 learners are able to comply with the rules of utilizing linguistic elements or properties that make well-constructed statements. However, there may be instances that complicated syntax requirements may cause slight errors among the grade 7 learners.

Still at the 7-above mean range, the students were able to perform better in abbreviation compared to other grammar skills, $M(101)=7.04$, $sd=2.21$, $SEM=.220$. This mean score is interpreted as satisfactory according to the scale interpretation (CI 95% = 6.61, 7.47). The level therefore of the grade 7 students when it comes to grammar skills is proficient. This level can be described as a semantic competence or ability of the grade 7 learners to process a word and group of words to become shorter versions from its original form. On this aspect, the students also performed at the satisfactory level making them able to effectively process compounded words into abbreviated forms while maintaining its meaningfulness and usefulness.

Leveling at the 6-above mean range, the students performed better in capitalization ($M(101)=6.86$, $sd=1.76$, $SEM=.175$), than in punctuation ($M(101)=6.36$, $sd=2.04$, $SEM=.203$). While they differ on the mean scores, the scale interpretation still falls within the satisfactory level (CI 95% = 6.52, 7.26; CI 95% = 5.96, 6.76). This indicates that the grade 7 learners are both capable of utilizing capitalization techniques in sentences when it is appropriate while also being able to make use of the necessary punctuation markers across various statement intents.

The relative weakest performance in the test was the area on sentence structure, $M(101)=6.10$, $sd=2.74$, $SEM=.272$. This is where the true level of the grade 7 learners may vary using the hypothetical mean range (CI 95% = 5.57, 6.63) which is interpreted from the scale belonging to fair to satisfactory level. This means that there is a probability that the grade 7 learners' level of proficiency may fall between fair and satisfactory. This indicates that sentence structure may pose more difficulty among the grade 7 learners compared to other levels.

The results that were mentioned above was supported in the study conducted by Burns (2014). He found out that the reason why students have a better performance in spelling because the fact that text abbreviation was largely phonetically based. He also added, when students are playing with creative representations of language they have to use and rehearse their understanding of letter-sound correspondences: a skill which is taught formally as phonics in primary classrooms.

Over-all Level of English Grammar Skills of the Grade 7 Learners

Table 10 displayed over-all level of English grammar skills of the grade 7 learners were regarded as proficient ($M(101)=41.158$, $sd=9.720$, $SEM = .967$).

The real mean of the over-all English grammar skills of the grade 7 learners may hypothetically range from a 95% confidence interval of 39.26 to 43.05 mean score, which also translates to a proficient level. Table 9.1 also illustrated that the grade 7 learner respondents have firm grasp of essential skills in grammar and were able to master the basics of the grammar assessment. This further illustrated

that the grade 7 learner respondents commit occasional or infrequent errors when it comes to constructing a grammatically sound statements, as well as, utilizing grammar-related requirements such as abbreviation, punctuation, and capitalization.

Table 10. *Over-all Level of English Grammar Skills of the Grade 7 Learners*

	Mean	SD	Standard Error of the Mean	CI 95%		Interpretation
				Upper	Lower	
Over-all English Grammar Skills	41.158	9.720	.967	43.05	39.26	Proficient level

Problem 3. Is there a significant relationship between texting characteristics and the English Grammar skills of Grade 7 students?

Table 11 displayed the type of messages sent and the level of English grammar skills of the grade 7 learners, the Pearson product-moment correlation test in table 11 revealed select significant correlations.

Table 11. *Correlation Analysis between Respondent Characteristics (Types of Messages Sent) and Level of English Grammar Skills of the Grade 7 Learners*

	Pearson		Interpretation	Decision
	r	p-value		
Spelling	-.022	.829	Accept H0	Accept H0
Syntax	.144	.151	Accept H0	Accept H0
Sentence Structure	-.041	.687	Accept H0	Accept H0
Abbreviation	-.204*	.041	Negative, Weak, Significant	Reject H0
Punctuation	-.072	.472	Accept H0	Accept H0
Capitalization	-.014	.890	Accept H0	Accept H0

*significant at $p < .05$ **significant at $p < .01$ ***significant at $p < .001$

Pearson r legend: .00-.19 – Negligible to very weak relationship; .20-.39 – weak relationship; .40-.59 – moderate relationship; .60-.79 – strong relationship; .80-.99 – very strong relationship

As observe in the table above, there is a significant and negative correlation between type of messages sent and abbreviation ($r(100) = -.426$, $p < .001$), hence, rejecting the null hypothesis. The results further reveal a negative low correlation between type of messages sent and abbreviation. This suggests that an increase in the use of text messaging for other purposes may have a significantly induce low decrease in the correct notation for abbreviation.

Such relationship may be described such that as the grade 7 learners increase the number of texting to more types of communicating, their performance in the skill of abbreviation may significantly decrease. The opposite of this analysis may also hold true, that statistically, a significant increase in the grammar skills may happen when they reduce the use of texting for communication purposes. This implies that using texting to communicate to a lot of purposes may have negative implication to their English grammar skills, specifically on abbreviation.

Correlation Analysis between Respondent Characteristics (Common words being shortcut) and Level of English Grammar Skills of the Grade 7 Learners

Table 12 displayed common words being shortcut and level of English grammar skills, the Pearson product-moment correlation test in table 12 revealed select significant correlations.

Table 12. *Correlation Analysis between Respondent Characteristics (Common words being shortcut) and Level of English Grammar Skills of the Grade 7 Learners*

	Pearson		Interpretation	Decision
	r	p-value		
Spelling	-.253*	.011	Negative, Weak, Significant	Reject H0
Syntax	-.197*	.048	Negative, Weak, Significant	Reject H0
Sentence Structure	-.133	.186	Negative, Not Significant	Accept H0
Abbreviation	-.421***	<.001	Negative, Moderate, Significant	Reject H0
Punctuation	-.217*	.029	Negative, Weak, Significant	Reject H0
Capitalization	-.234*	.018	Negative, Weak, Significant	Reject H0

*significant at $p < .05$ **significant at $p < .01$ ***significant at $p < .001$

Pearson r legend: .00-.19 – Negligible to very weak relationship; .20-.39 – weak relationship; .40-.59 – moderate relationship; .60-.79 – strong relationship; .80-.99 – very strong relationship

As observe in the table above, there is a significant and negative correlation between words being shortcut and spelling ($r(100) = -.253$, $p = .011$), syntax ($r(100) = -.197$, $p = .048$), abbreviation ($r(100) = -.421$, $p < .001$), and punctuation ($r(100) = -.217$, $p = .029$) and capitalization ($r(100) = -.234$, $p = .018$), hence, rejecting the null hypothesis. The results further reveal a negative medium correlation between common words being short cut and abbreviation. This however, suggests that an increase of using the commonly shortcut words in text messaging may have induce a significantly moderate decrease or reduction in the correct notation of abbreviation. Also, there is a low and negative degree of relationship between use of commonly short cut words with spelling, syntax, punctuation and abbreviation

which means that there may be a low decrease or reduction in the in these areas when there is an increase in the usage of shortcut text messaging words.

Correlation Analysis between Respondent Characteristics (Consciousness to Grammatical Structure) and Level of English Grammar Skills of the Grade 7 Learners

Table 13 displayed the existence of all significant correlation between respondent characteristics in terms of consciousness to grammatical structure and the level of English grammar skills.

Table 13. *Correlation Analysis between Respondent Characteristics (Consciousness to Grammatical Structure) and Level of English Grammar Skills of the Grade 7 Learners*

	Pearson		Interpretation	Decision
	r	p-value		
Spelling	.486***	<.001	Positive, Moderate, Significant	Reject H0
Syntax	.502***	<.001	Positive, Moderate, Significant	Reject H0
Sentence Structure	.435***	<.001	Positive, Moderate, Significant	Reject H0
Abbreviation	.516***	<.001	Positive, Moderate, Significant	Reject H0
Punctuation	.260**	.009	Positive, Weak, Significant	Reject H0
Capitalization	.399***	<.001	Positive, Moderate, Significant	Reject H0

*significant at $p < .05$ **significant at $p < .01$ ***significant at $p < .001$

Pearson r legend: .00-.19 – Negligible to very weak relationship; .20-.39 – weak relationship; .40-.59 – moderate relationship; .60-.79 – strong relationship; .80-.99 – very strong relationship

Specifically, there is a significant and positive correlation between consciousness to grammatical structure and spelling ($r(100) = .486$, $p < .001$), syntax ($r(100) = .502$, $p < .001$), sentence structure ($r(100) = .435$, $p < .001$), abbreviation ($r(100) = .516$, $p < .001$), punctuation ($r(100) = .260$, $p = .009$) and capitalization ($r(100) = .399$, $p < .001$), hence, successfully and fully rejecting the null hypothesis. The results also reveal a positive direction of these correlations such that an increase in the level of the learners' consciousness to grammatical structure increases the level of their grammar skills.

This result is also supported in the study conducted by Tag (2009), her study concluded that student's consciousness of the English language use is not negatively associated with dealing with standard of literacy of English grammar rather it boosted their spelling skills, sentence construction and expressing themselves through texting. They can assist them in developing their grammar skills as a means of communication, upgrading their skills in this new form of writing.

Problem 4. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' exposure to texting and their English Grammar skills level?

Table 14 displayed duration of texting English and level English grammar skills, the Pearson product-moment correlation test in table 14 revealed select significant correlations.

Table 14. *Correlation Analysis between Respondent Characteristics (Duration of Texting English) and Level of English Grammar Skills of the Grade 7 Learners*

	Pearson		Interpretation	Decision
	r	p-value		
Spelling	-.424***	<.001	Negative, Moderate, Significant	Reject H0
Syntax	-.052	.605	Negative, Not Significant	Accept H0
Sentence Structure	-.259**	.009	Negative, Weak, Significant	Reject H0
Abbreviation	-.395***	<.001	Negative, Moderate, Significant	Reject H0
Punctuation	-.125	.213	Negative, Not Significant	Accept H0
Capitalization	-.207*	.038	Negative, Weak, Significant	Reject H0

*significant at $p < .05$ **significant at $p < .01$ ***significant at $p < .001$

Pearson r legend: .00-.19 – Negligible to very weak relationship; .20-.39 – weak relationship; .40-.59 – moderate relationship; .60-.79 – strong relationship; .80-.99 – very strong relationship

As stated in the table above, there is a significant and negative correlation between duration of texting English and spelling ($r(100) = -.424$, $p < .001$), capitalization ($r(100) = -.207$, $p = .038$), abbreviation ($r(100) = -.395$, $p < .001$), and sentence structure ($r(100) = -.259$, $p < .001$) hence, rejecting the null hypothesis. The results further reveal a negative low correlation of English grammar skills with capitalization and sentence structure while a moderate correlation with spelling and abbreviation. This suggests that an increase in duration of texting English may induce medium to low reduction in the level of English grammar skills of the grade 7 learners in areas of spelling and abbreviation and then capitalization and sentence structure, respectively.

The result was supported by Sermsook et al. (2017) they tested the language errors in the writings of twenty-six Thai EFL students, and observed that capitalization and abbreviation error are one of the most regularly committed mistakes made through the learners. The researcher administered a specifically designed test made from 24 punctuation fill-in-the-blank items and 6 capitalization error identity items, and observed that capitalization errors had been the most common mistakes made by the participants.

Correlation Analysis between Respondent Characteristics (Frequency of Shortcut) and Level of English Grammar Skills of the Grade 7 Learners

Table 15 displayed the frequency of shortcut and level English grammar skills, the Pearson product-moment correlation test in table 15 revealed select significant correlations.

Table 15. *Correlation Analysis between Respondent Characteristics (Frequency of Shortcut) and Level of English Grammar Skills of the Grade 7 Learners*

	Pearson		Interpretation	Decision
	r	p-value		
Spelling	-.426***	<.001	Negative, Moderate, Significant	Reject H0
Syntax	-.388***	<.001	Negative, Moderate, Significant	Reject H0
Sentence Structure	-.126	.208	Negative, not significant	Accept H0
Abbreviation	-.366***	<.001	Negative, Moderate, Significant	Reject H0
Punctuation	-.272***	<.001	Negative, Weak, Significant	Reject H0
Capitalization	-.002	.987	Negative, not significant	Accept H0

*significant at $p < .05$ **significant at $p < .01$ ***significant at $p < .001$
 Pearson r legend: .00-.19 – Negligible to very weak relationship; .20-.39 – weak relationship; .40-.59-moderate relationship;
 60-.79 – strong relationship; .80-.99 – very strong relationship

Specifically, there is a significant and negative correlation between frequency of shortcuts and spelling ($r(100) = -.426$, $p < .001$), syntax ($r(100) = -.388$, $p < .001$), abbreviation ($r(100) = -.366$, $p < .001$), and punctuation ($r(100) = -.272$, $p < .001$), hence, rejecting the null hypothesis. The results further reveal a negative low correlation between frequency of shortcut and punctuation. This however, suggests that an increase of shortcut usage in text messaging may have a significantly low reduction in the correct punctuation. Also, there is a moderate degree of relationship between frequency of shortcuts with spelling, syntax and abbreviation which means that there may be a moderate decrease in the performance of spelling, syntax and abbreviation when there is an increase in the usage of shortcuts.

They tend to commit error in using the correct punctuation in their writing activities.

However, in the majority of studies, students use of texting and their grammar skills and literacy abilities were found to be positively related, accuracy of spelling, correct usage of punctuation and sentence structure were positively associated.

Correlation Analysis between Respondent Characteristics (Extent of use of English in Text Messaging) and Level of English Grammar Skills of the Grade 7 Learners

Table 16 displayed extent of use of English in text messaging and level of English grammar skills, the Pearson product-moment correlation test in table 16 revealed the existence of all significant correlations.

Table 16. *Correlation Analysis between Respondent Characteristics (Extent of use of English in Text Messaging) and Level of English Grammar Skills of the Grade 7 Learners*

	Pearson		Interpretation	Decision
	r	p-value		
Spelling	-.421***	<.001	Negative, Moderate, Significant	Reject H0
Syntax	-.463***	<.001	Negative, Moderate, Significant	Reject H0
Sentence Structure	-.444***	<.001	Negative, Moderate, Significant	Reject H0
Abbreviation	-.362***	<.001	Negative, Weak, Significant	Reject H0
Punctuation	-.228*	.022	Negative, Weak, Significant	Reject H0
Capitalization	-.314***	.001	Negative, Weak, Significant	Reject H0

*significant at $p < .05$ **significant at $p < .01$ ***significant at $p < .001$
 Pearson r legend: .00-.19 – Negligible to very weak relationship; .20-.39 – weak relationship; .40-.59-moderate relationship;
 60-.79 – strong relationship; .80-.99 – very strong relationship

Conclusions

After an intensive analysis of the data, it was concluded that the respondents had a poor performance toward texting and considered it to have a negative implication on their English grammar skills. Students use words in texting which are not general in Standard English. Texting gave birth to a few words, which the students extensively utilize in their oral and written communication. It became apparent that students have trouble with sentence structure. It was also found that students do now no longer examine the sentence structure every time they may be requested to construct a sentence. They have low scores on the abbreviation test and result in differences in understanding of single words because there are agreed-upon on guidelines for abbreviating words. This led to ambiguity, and the reader might not be capable of guessing the supposed meaning. They fail to determine the correct syntax of the sentence as they have low scores in the test being administered. They do not know how to punctuate their sentences. Even using the proper capitalization has been influenced by texting.

Based on the findings and conclusions presented in the study action plan has been drawn for Grade 7 teachers and should be implemented for grade 7 students.

In view of the findings presented and conclusions made, as teachers, it's far essential then to offer students with lessons that are not only well-based however that are additionally exciting and enjoyable. Careful thought and preparation will assist to attain this. When considering an English lessons, it's far beneficial to maintain the subsequent 3 factors in mind engage, study and activate.

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